

THE ROLE OF COLLEGES IN VALUE EDUCATION

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Apart from imparting moral values, education also aims at generating a social awareness among the students. Saswat S. Das analyzes value education in following words:

“Value-education in synthesis carries on the art of reconciling ethics, morality and religion with scientific progress”.

The college should provide enough space for enhancing the students’ ability in both mental and physical sense.

The classroom teaching aims at the enhancement of mental faculties of a student where as her physical faculties are nurtured on playgrounds or through the co-curricular activities like NCC and NSS.

National Cadet Corps (NCC) was established in the year 1948 as an organization. It carries all along with it its motto-“Ekta Aur Anushasan” – ‘Unity and Discipline’ and plans to mould a youth by developing in her the essential qualities like discipline, courage, comradeship and sportsmanship. It has always aimed to create a human resource of organized, trained and motivated youth who walk successfully on all walks of life and who will readily offer their services for the nation, when the nation needs them. It is NCC which imparts to her the greatest value of human life – SACRIFICE.

Man, basically is a social being and needs to understand his responsibility towards his society and so it becomes obligatory for the students to understand properly the social environment in which they live. The other activity, National Service Scheme (NSS) with an emblem of wheel symbolising movement works out with an aim – “The development of the personality of students through community service”. It intends to make the students familiar with the community and strengthen their relations with the community. This service aims to develop among the students a sense of social and civic responsibility. It provides the students the basic understanding of sharing and living with each other as well as getting to know the issues and problems of the society they live in!

Both the services impart moral righteousness, helping the students to understand various problems of society and the plausible and possible ways out to resolve them. Both these agencies work for resolving alienation and rationalizing diversity. Group activities and field work cater to the most important training-

physical, mental, intellectual training of the youth. Activities like camping impart physical training like gun shooting, horse riding, for physical fitness and yoga and medication for mental equilibrium. Classroom teaching in NCC imparts the skills like map reading, and knowing their geography well. Field work leads them to community services.

An activity likes ‘Sports’ definitely is of great help in imbibing different values in students. Sports imbibe participation at all levels. In it the player are not active only in a physical sense but they have to be fully focused and have to keep all their senses alert to reach to the goal. The participants learn very important lesson that there is no short-cut to reach to the destination. Sincere efforts and hard work can be the only ways to translate the dreams into reality. Through participation in sports students can learn the significance of honesty, sincerity, integrity and hard work. Formal education falls short of equipping our students with these life-making values and that is why most of our youth face failure and frustration in different walks of life.

It is sports that give a concrete direction, meaning and profundity. Defeat and victory are the part of the game. Players learn to take both the things in their stride with equal courage and modesty. Sports provide all essential ingredients for the all-round development of personality, independent thinking and leadership qualities and ultimately it helps to bring social harmony. As Dr.Purushottam and Dr.Antony Stella has observed that “according to the social psychologists, leadership is a special phenomenon arising from group action: It is not considered as a special property or gift of an individual. Although some people appear to possess more of the characteristics conducive to it than other, leadership occurs in group action.”

Thus, through group activities like sports, NSS and NCC, the students acquire basic important skills and learn an important lesson that sincere efforts and hard work are the only ways to translate the dreams to reality. Through participation in these college activities, one can learn the significance of discipline, harmony, sincerity, integrity and hard work. Also one can experience the universal human values like truth, non-violence, love and compassion through these activities. It is here a student gets the initial lessons of democratic setting, which helps her later on, in her own, walk of life. And education in its formal or informal form, has always imparted a wisdom for a moral and ethical walk of life.

References:

Das, Saswat, *Return to Innocence: Value Education in the Postmodern Age*, Vol.41, University News, 2003.

Adishesah Malcolm S, *Role of Universities as Agents of Change in Higher Education in the Eighties: Opportunities and Objectives*. Edited by J.Vera Raghvan, New Delhi, Lancer International, 1985.

Purushottam and Antony Stella, *Educational Innovations*. New Delhi, 1995, p.42

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